

Model-Free Optimization of Isolated DC-DC Triple Active Bridge Converters for ZVS and Reduced RMS Current Operation

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Abstract—Isolated multi-port converters (IMPCs) find applications across several domains. The triple active bridge converter (TAB) is an IMPC that interconnects three dc ports via a three-terminal high-frequency transformer. TAB operation allows zero voltage switching (ZVS) without requiring additional snubber circuits. However, specific loading conditions may lead to loss of ZVS and increased rms currents. Remarking the benefits of ZVS include enhanced efficiency, improved reliability, and reduced EMI noises, the paper proposes a model-free online optimization employing multi-dimensional ripple correlation search (MD-RCC) to ensure ZVS optimization while concurrently reducing rms currents. The MD-RCC features the advantages of being online and model-free, thus endowing the proposed solution robustness against parameter uncertainties or variations due to changes in operating conditions.

Index Terms—Triple active bridge (TAB), multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC), zero voltage switching (ZVS).

I. INTRODUCTION

Isolated multi-port converters (IMPCs) offer several potential advantages, including high efficiency, high power density, and galvanic isolation among the ports [1]. These merits are commonly attained by exploiting a multi-terminal high-frequency transformer (HFT) to facilitate interfacing ports with different voltage or current ratings [1]. IMPCs fit into several applications, such as dc microgrids and electric vehicles [2], [3]. The triple active bridge converter (TAB), displayed in Fig. 1 [4], is an IMPC with three ports, and it can be considered as an extension to an additional port of the dual active bridge (DAB) [5]. TAB comprises a three-terminal HFT connected to three bridges [4]. The HFT plays a crucial role in interfacing the dc ports and allowing a controlled energy transfer path through its leakage inductances L_1L_2 , and L_3 [4].

Phase shift modulation (PSM), represented in Fig. 2(a), can be utilized to control the power flow in TABs [4]. To this end, considering v_1 as a reference, PSM concerns the definition of the external phase shifts ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 of the generated ac voltages v_2 and v_3 . PSM is a straightforward modulation scheme featuring low conduction losses and the capability to achieve zero voltage switching (ZVS) in some operating conditions. However, PSM operation may significantly depart from the optimal condition, where high losses emerge at low power transfer and/or when the voltage ratios of the

Fig. 1: TAB converter

ports are not matched with the transformer turns ratio, i.e., $V_2/V_1 \neq n_2/n_1$ and $V_3/V_1 \neq n_3/n_1$ [4]. Multiphase-shift modulation (MPSM), shown in Fig. 2(b), was introduced to overcome PSM limitations by exploiting internal phase shifts too, namely the duty-cycles D_1, D_2 , and D_3 of the voltages v_1, v_2 , and v_3 , respectively [4]. MPSM allows tuning TAB operation by adjusting these duty-cycles aiming at operating points with reduced rms and full ZVS operation.

While optimizing the operating efficiency is a renowned fundamental objective [4], [6]–[14], securing ZVS operation throughout the entire range of operation also presents remarkable advantages, including those outlined next. *i)* Enhanced efficiency at high switching frequencies: the utilization of wide-bandgap semiconductors (i.e., SiC, GaN) elevates the switching frequency, reducing the size of the passives [15]. However, switching losses have higher impacts at higher switching frequencies. ZVS abates turn-on losses of the switches, which is a significant part of the switching loss [15]. *ii)* Improved reliability: reduced switching loss means that devices are subjected to less thermal stress. Additionally, ZVS helps prevent undesired voltage ringings, which is also associated with reduced component stresses and overall better reliability [16]. *iii)* Reduced EMI: ZVS ensures, by definition, soft switching transitions, which are associated with lower gen-

Fig. 2: Switching sequence of TAB modulation schemes: (a) phase-shift modulation (PSM); (b) multiphase-shift modulation (MPSM).

erated electromagnetic noise [17]. *iv*) Lessen snubber circuits requirements: TAB operation can be exploited to achieve ZVS over the whole operating range by a proper modulation scheme [15].

ZVS conditions of TABs have been discussed in several works. In [6], a ZVS criterion that considers all TAB parameters has been introduced, but neglecting conduction losses. Alternatively, [7] established a universal analytical model for the TAB using a frequency domain analysis, accompanied by a particle swarm algorithm that minimizes rms current while meeting ZVS constraints. Despite their efficacy, the optimizations introduced in [6] and [7] rely on complex analytical models of TAB and, due to the use of given look-up tables, they lack the flexibility to adapt to the actual hardware and operating conditions.

In the following, a model-free online optimization for TAB based on multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC) is proposed. MD-RCC has been applied to optimize the rms current of TAB in [14] and the efficiency of the QAB in [18]. However, this method is originally applied herein to optimize ZVS and reduce rms current, which also allows valuable converter performance in terms of overall conversion efficiency. The proposed approach offers both online and model-free advantages, allowing for online adaptation to potential parameter changes such as resistances, inductances, deadtime, switching frequency, etc.

II. OPTIMAL MODULATION OF TAB CONVERTERS

PSM is a straightforward modulation scheme employed to regulate the power flow in TABs, as shown in Fig. 2(a). By the PSM, the external phase shifts, ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 , between the three bridges, considering the first bridge as a reference, are adjusted to control the power flow, directing it from the leading to the lagging port, with the theoretical maximum at a phase shift of $\pi/2$ [4]. The external phase shift ϕ_2 represents the displacement between the switching of S_1 and S_5 , likewise ϕ_3

Fig. 3: Simulation results of TAB; (a)-(b) total rms current for PSM and GSO, respectively; (c)-(d) percentage of devices achieving ZVS ($N_{\%}^{ZVS}$) for PSM and GSO, respectively. Converter parameters as in Table I of Sec. IV.

is the shift between S_1 and S_9 , as shown in Fig. 2(a). However, PSM leads to high losses, especially with low transferred power and mismatches among the ports voltage ratios and the transformer turns ratio. This brings increased rms current, increasing joule losses, as well as loss of ZVS. Instead, by MPSM, the internal phase shift between two legs within a full bridge is controlled beside the external phase shifts in order to alleviate the issue [4]. The internal phase shift for each bridge is represented by the duty-cycle of the corresponding bridge, namely, D_1, D_2 , and D_3 for the three bridges, as shown in Fig. 2(b). The internal phase shift represents the shift between the switching instances of S_1 and S_4 for port-1, controlling D_1 , as shown in Fig. 2(b); analogously for port-2 and 3.

A. Optimizing MPSM for Minimum rms Current

With the additional degrees of freedom, namely, D_1, D_2 , and D_3 , improved TAB operation can be obtained. In [11]–[14], the pursuit of minimizing the joule losses involves reducing the rms currents flowing through the converter, pursued herein by the measure (1).

$$i^{rms} = \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^3 i_{n,rms}^2} \quad (1)$$

To show the effectiveness of MPSM over PSM, a grid search optimization (GSO) is carried out to determine the optimum duty-cycles (i.e., D_1, D_2 , and D_3) for minimum total rms

current. The GSO systematically explores all possible combinations of duty-cycles for a TAB converter with parameters outlined in Table I, using a PLECS simulation. Meanwhile, the phase shifts (i.e., ϕ_2 and ϕ_3) are adjusted using a pair of regulators to control the power exchange at port-2 and port-3. The simulation is designed to consider various loading conditions. Port-1 and 2 voltages remain constant at their rated values, while port-3 voltage varies from 0.6 to 1.4 the rated voltage. In this setup, the power flows from port-1 to ports-2 and 3. Port-2 power is constant at 100 W, while port-3 power changes from 100 W to the rated power. The GSO is employed with a resolution step of 0.05 on the duty-cycles.

Fig. 3(b) shows that the rms current by the GSO is reduced as compared to Fig. 3(a). The recorded reductions score up to 80% of the original value with the PSM. Such a substantial decrease in total rms current is particularly valuable in scenarios of low-power operation with voltage mismatch.

B. Optimizing MPSM for Enhanced ZVS and Reduced rms Current

To compare the effectiveness of different modulation schemes in achieving ZVS, criteria to discern ZVS should be defined first. As detailed in [19], the criteria used herein is based on the computation of the minimum threshold current i_{th} necessary to discharge the parasitic capacitance C_{eq} of a switching device initially operating at voltage V_{ds} and assuming a fixed discharge current during a given available deadtime $t_{deadtime}$:

$$i_{th} = \frac{2V_{ds}C_{eq}}{t_{deadtime}} \quad (2)$$

For example, considering the parameters in Table I, the calculated threshold current is 400 mA. For a single leg comprising two switches, namely S_1 and S_2 , as illustrated in Fig. 1, with current and voltage directions indicated, the ZVS conditions are as follows.

- 1) The upper switch S_1 achieves full ZVS if the turn-on current i_{S1_on} is less than the negative threshold value, that is, $i_{S1_on} < -i_{th}$.
- 2) The lower switch S_2 achieves full ZVS if the turn-on current i_{S2_on} is greater than the positive threshold value, that is, $i_{S2_on} > +i_{th}$.

Based on these conditions, the percentage of devices satisfying the ZVS criteria is assessed and referred to as $N_{\%}^{ZVS}$. The results are illustrated in Fig. 3(c) for PSM and in Fig. 3(d) for GSO referring to (1). It is worth noting that the GSO objective is exclusively to identify points with the lowest rms current, regardless of ZVS conditions. Consequently, the attained ZVS profiles are incidental.

To show that operation with all transitions in ZVS can be reached with MPSM, the GSO is modified to search for minimum rms current restricted within the subset in which full or partial ZVS is realized. Fig. 4 displays the GSO iterations for the test case in Fig. 3 with port-3 power at 100 W and port-3 voltage at 240 V. For the GSO aiming to minimize the rms current only, iteration #2 gives the best outcome, yielding a

Fig. 4: Total rms current and the corresponding number of hard switching devices for each iteration of GSO.

total rms current of 2.17 A with six devices in hard-switching, that is, $N_{\%}^{ZVS} = 50\%$. Differently, when integrating ZVS as a requirement for the GSO solutions, iteration #95 yields a total rms current of 3.26 A with zero hard switching devices, achieving 100% ZVS.

Noticeably, pursuing minimum rms current within a subset featuring all the transitions in ZVS might lead to an increase in the total rms current. However, this outcome is also dependent on the GSO resolution step: a finer step could potentially locate better solutions with lower rms currents. Additionally, even with the modified GSO, the obtained rms current still demonstrates a significant reduction as compared to the PSM marked at approximately 11 A.

III. ONLINE MODEL-FREE OPTIMIZATION OF TAB

In Sect.II, MPSM shows the ability to attain full or partial ZVS and reduce the flowing rms currents. However, the employed GSO exhibits drawbacks, including a substantial time requirement for data collection, a significant computational burden with a small resolution step, and the necessity to store results in look-up tables. Additionally, the GSO lacks the adaptability to accommodate parameter changes in the converter resulting from variations in operating conditions. Hence, an online model-free optimization method has been implemented to optimize the performance of the TAB with full or partial ZVS operation and with reduced rms currents. The optimization approach utilized herein is known as multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC), initially introduced in [14] to optimize the rms current of the TAB converter and in [18] to optimize the efficiency of the QAB. However, its application to optimize the ZVS operation of TAB has not been explored previously.

MD-RCC is based on the operating principle of the ripple correlation control (RCC), also known as extremum-seeking control (ESC) [20]. In RCC, the optimization of a specific cost function involves imposing a perturbation on the control variable. The correlation between the applied perturbation and the cost function is then identified. Subsequently, the control

Fig. 5: Multi-dimensional ripple correlation search (MD-RCC).

variable is adjusted, guided by the estimated correlation, in the direction of either maximizing or minimizing the cost function. In order to optimize a given cost function with multiple degrees of freedom, *corresponding* perturbations are superimposed on the control variables, herein duty-cycles D_1, D_2 , and D_3 . These perturbations must possess distinct frequencies. This allows for independently measuring the correlation between the cost function and each perturbation, thanks to the orthogonality among the perturbations and the corresponding effects. The imposed perturbations can be defined as

$$\epsilon \sin \omega_p t, \quad p = 1, 2, 3 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 5 shows the implementation of MD-RCC. The low-pass filters (LPF) serve as an approximation of the moving average. Consequently, these filters should be designed with a cutoff frequency sufficiently lower than the minimum perturbation frequency. Additionally, the stability considerations in [14] must be considered:

- 1) The maximum perturbation frequency should be much slower than the plant dynamics (i.e., the plant is considered as a static map w.r.t the maximum correlation perturbation).
- 2) The perturbation frequencies should be different to guarantee orthogonality.
- 3) The low pass filters should have a cutoff frequency lower than the lowest difference between the perturbation frequencies.
- 4) The perturbation magnitude should have a very small value compared to the possible optimum (e.g., 1% of full duty-cycle).

To simultaneously maintain low rms currents and optimize ZVS operation, a novel cost function is introduced herein:

$$I_{ZVS}^{rms} = K_{rms} \cdot i^{rms} + K_{ZVS} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{n_{device}} H \cdot I_{n,HS}^2} \quad (4)$$

where, K_{rms} and K_{ZVS} are weighting factors, i^{rms} is the total rms current as defined in (1), n is the number of switches

Fig. 6: Hard switching current detection algorithm of the TAB in Fig. 1; i_{th} calculated with (2).

TABLE I: TAB parameters.

Parameters	Value	
Nominal power at each port P_{rated}	kW	5
Switching frequency $f_s = 1/T_s$	kHz	40
Rated dc voltages V_1-V_3	V	400
Transf. turns ratio $n_1 : n_2 : n_3$		1:1:1
Transf. leakage inductances $L_1 - L_3$	μH	44
Switching Devices	Cree C2M0080120D	
Dead time	μs	0.2
Sinusoidal perturbation magnitude ϵ	0.0025	
Weights K_{rms}, K_{ZVS}	5, 10	
Perturbation frequencies $\omega_1-\omega_3$	rad/s	$10\pi, 14\pi, 18\pi,$

($n = 1, \dots, 12$), H indicates whether the device is hard or soft switching, specifically, $H = 1$ for hard switching devices (i.e., ZVS criteria are not met), $H = 0$ for soft switching devices, and $I_{n,HS}$ denotes the switched current at the switching instant. The online computational procedure of $I_{n,HS}$ is shown in Fig. 6. The cost function includes the overall rms current of the TAB, combined with the hard switching commutation currents.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

To evaluate the effectiveness of the defined cost function, the MD-RCC-based approach was implemented in a simulation model using PLECS, with parameters listed in Table I. The test scenario in Sect. II was considered to assess the optimization capability of the approach and the defined cost function in achieving ZVS for all the switches over a comprehensive set of operating conditions. For each combination of port-3 power and voltage, the MD-RCC is executed to minimize the proposed cost function (4), which takes into account both total rms current and the hard switching currents if ZVS criteria defined in Sect. II-B are not satisfied. This process steers the converter operation away from unfavorable operating conditions for ZVS while sliding towards operating points with low rms currents.

Fig. 7 shows the results of applying the MD-RCC considering the minimization of the total rms current i^{rms} (1) versus

Fig. 7: Simulation results of MD-RCC with TAB: (a)-(b) total rms current of MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} in (1), and I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (4), respectively; (c)-(d) percentage devices achieving ZVS ($N_{ZVS}^{\%}$) of MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} in (1), and I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (4), respectively.

the proposed cost function I_{ZVS}^{rms} (4). As compared to rms currents minimization displayed in Fig. 7(a), the use of the proposed cost function leads to approximately equivalent rms currents in Fig. 7(b). However, by the proposed cost function, nearly all the switches satisfy the ZVS criterion, as shown in Fig. 7(d). This desirable result is not achieved using (1), as shown in Fig. 7(c), because such a cost function disregards switching conditions (i.e., soft or hard switching).

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

An experimental prototype has been developed with the parameters listed in Table I. The experimental prototype is displayed in Fig. 8. To implement the cost function (4), an NI PXIe-1082 has been employed to oversample the HFT currents. The B-box RCP is utilized to control the Imperix power modules and to execute the proposed MD-RCC. A power analyzer PW8001 by Hioki has been utilized to monitor TAB efficiency and losses.

To validate the performance of the proposed optimization, several operating conditions have been considered. Herein, a test case is shown at which power is transferred from port-1 to ports-2 and 3, with $V_1 = 400$ V, $V_2 = 280$ V, $V_3 = 320$ V, $P_2 = 100$ W, and $P_3 = 600$ W. This test case is chosen at a low power level and with voltages mismatched to the transformer turns ratios to demonstrate the advantage of the proposed optimization in a relevant operating condition.

Fig. 8: TAB experimental prototype.

Fig. 9: (a), (b), and (c) dynamic response of MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} (1): (a) duty-cycles; (b) total rms current; (c) sum of hard switching current; (d), (e), and (f) dynamic response of MD-RCC optimizing i_{ZVS}^{rms} (4): (d) duty-cycles; (e) total rms current; (f) sum of hard switching current.

Fig. 9(a), (b), and (c) illustrate the dynamic response of the proposed MD-RCC optimizing only the total rms current i^{rms} (1). Fig. 9(a) shows the duty-cycles optimization aimed at minimizing i^{rms} , as shown in Fig. 9(b). The MD-RCC reduces the total rms current from approximately 7.5 A at initial steady-state to about 5.5 A at final steady-state, achieving a reduction of approximately 27% from the initial value. However, optimizing considering the total rms current solely does not ensure soft switching operation, as highlighted in Fig. 9(c): the sum of the hard-switching currents is reduced but not zeroed, indicating that hard-switching devices are still present.

Fig. 9(d), (e), and (f) illustrate the dynamic response of the

(a) Initial state: total rms = 7.5 A, total hard switching current = 11.8 A, hard switching devices = 8.

(b) MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} : total rms = 5.5 A, total hard switching current = 5.1 A, hard switching devices = 4.

(c) MD-RCC optimizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} : total rms = 5.6 A, total hard switching current = 0 A, hard switching devices = 0.

● soft turn-on transition ● hard turn-on transition

Fig. 10: Transformer voltage and current steady-state waveforms of the test case in Fig. 9: (a) at the initial state; (b) after MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} (1); after MD-RCC optimizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} (4).

proposed MD-RCC when optimizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} as defined in (4). The optimization goal of the MD-RCC is to minimize the combination of both the total rms current, as shown in Fig. 9(e), and the hard switching current, as depicted in Fig. 9(f).

Fig. 9(e) indicates a reduction in the total rms current, comparable to the reduction observed in Fig. 9(b). However, because the cost function I_{ZVS}^{rms} includes the hard switching current as an optimization target, Fig. 9(f) shows a reduction of the hard switching current, which is zeroed in steady state, indicating the elimination of hard switching devices by the end of the optimization process.

Fig. 10 shows the steady-state voltage and current waveforms of the HFT. Fig. 10(a) shows the waveforms at the initial state, where 8 switching devices have hard turn-on transition, indicated by red dots for ports-2 and 3. Fig. 10(b) shows the steady-state waveforms after optimizing i^{rms} (1), a reduction in the total rms current is evident. However, 4 switching devices remain in a hard turn-on transition, as shown for port-2. Fig. 10(c) illustrates the steady-state waveforms after optimizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} (4). The total rms current is reduced compared to the initial state, with complete soft switching transitions achieved

for the three active bridges of the converter.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates the feasibility of achieving a trade-off between zero voltage switching (ZVS) operation and reduced rms current for the triple active bridge converter (TAB). Initially, a comprehensive grid search optimization (GSO) is employed to find the minimum rms current within a subset of points that achieve either partial or full ZVS. Subsequently, a multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC) is utilized to optimize a novel cost function that accounts for both rms current and hard switching currents. The results of the MD-RCC search highlight its advantages of being online, model-free, and adaptable to parameter changes online. While the optimization of the new cost function may result in points with slightly higher total rms current compared to the absolute minimum, the primary goal is to balance the total rms current and the hard switching current. This trade-off not only impacts efficiency but also affects EMI noise levels and the lifetime of the converter. The proposed optimization algorithm is validated through extensive simulation and experimental test cases.

Additional investigations are being performed to improve the practical implementation of the approach and to show the benefits of the achievable operation regimes of converters exploiting the resulting optimal modulation parameters.

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